

Sustain-COAST

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Deliverable 4.4: Didactic materials for Partners training on mediation techniques

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¹ Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium, **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium

² Nature of the deliverable: **R** = Report, **P** = Prototype, **D** = Demonstrator, **O** = Other

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP: Work Package

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1 Sustain-COAST Project Overview

Sustain-COAST “Sustainable coastal groundwater management and pollution reduction through innovative governance in a changing climate” is an R&I project co-funded under the PRIMA 2018 programme section II, with a 3-year duration starting from June 2019. Sustain-COAST consortium is led by the Technical University of Crete (TUC) and is composed of a multidisciplinary team of seven partners from six countries.

Sustain-COAST aims to **explore new governance approaches** to effectively support coastal aquifer conservation against anthropogenic and climatic pressures, through the promotion of innovative water management concepts based on the 4R principles: **Reduce; Recycle; Reuse and Recover**.

Thanks to Sustain-COAST, new options will be available to private and public bodies for sustainable Mediterranean coastal groundwater management based on an **improved response-ability** of all concerned actors taking into account the local environmental and socio-economic context.

2 Objective

This deliverable aims to document the progress made in the implementation of Task 4.4 “Conflict mediation exploration”, which falls within WP4 (Innovative Governance).

WP4 includes the analysis and assessment of the different case studies’ water management governance systems, as well as the implementation of a process of stakeholder engagement through the setting up of participatory platforms, with the aim of triggering dialogue among different water-related stakeholders, using innovative approaches to promote transformative changes, and of **exploring mediation techniques for solving environmental water management-related conflicts** (Task 4.4). Therefore, as part of WP4, UNISS organised a **Summer School on environmental conflict mediation** for Project Partners and other candidates with appropriate backgrounds. This deliverable summarises the main didactic material used for partners’ training on environmental conflict mediation.

3 The Acqúa Summer School on Environmental Conflict Mediation

The **Acqúa Summer School on Environmental Conflict Mediation** was organized by the Desertification Research Center of the University of Sassari (NRD-UNISS) in Oristano (Sardinia, Italy) on 27th-30th June 2022.

The Acqúa Summer School covered the following topics:

1. Conflict analysis and specificity of environmental conflicts.

2. Analysis of environmental conflict cases (study of the escalation of the conflict, selection of the actors to be involved in the process, identification of interests, risk assessment and analysis of any damage...).
3. Best models and processes of mediation.
4. Mediation in relation to water-related conflicts, with case studies from the Mediterranean Region.

The approach of the Acqúa Summer School combined theoretical and practical activities, with case studies about **water-related conflicts from the Mediterranean Region**.

4 Training material on environmental conflict mediation

4.1 Environmental conflicts: from disputes to collaborative instruments

Across the world, communities are struggling to defend their land, air, water, forests and livelihoods from activities with severe environmental and social impacts (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Map of documented cases of social conflict around environmental issues

Source: <https://www.ejatl.org/>

Environmental conflicts are often triggered by or related to:

- Relation between man and nature, particularly in terms of **access, use and management of resources**.
- Equal **distribution** of risks and benefits.
- Awareness and **participation** in environmental policies.

Issues of **environmental and climate justice** are therefore also interlinked to issues of **social justice**. For instance, climate change has ethical, social and political implications (e.g. environmental racism, forced migrations...) and there is an asymmetry between those responsible for climate change and its victims. According to a Lancet research, 90% of pollution-related deaths (approx. 9 mil/year) occur in low or middle-income countries: in addition to outsourcing work, richer countries outsource deaths. Similarly, the richest areas of a country (but also of a city) outsource them to the most peripheral and vulnerable areas.

Therefore, **how do we face environmental and climate conflicts?** Environmental and climate conflicts are **multi-stakeholder, cross-scalar, unavoidable, unregulated**. Such **complexity** requires **multi-actor, cross-sectoral approaches**.

There are multiple ways of **managing and preventing** environmental and climate conflicts. For instance, the affected parties can go to trial. However, lawsuits have several limitations:

- i) Difficulties in demonstrating **causation links** and attributing **responsibilities**.
- ii) Difficulties in **establishing the affected party**, as environmental conflicts may be affecting a community instead of a single person.
- iii) It is often hard to demonstrate the **extent of the damage**, as the effects may not be immediately visible.
- iv) Even after establishing a sentence, parties tend to stall, and action is not taken immediately. This is due to the fact that, instead of encouraging dialogue and collectively elaborating shared options for the future, the focus tends to be on past wrongdoings.

This calls for the need to identify new strategies and tools to prevent and manage environmental conflicts. One example is given by collaborative practices such as **mediation**. Before illustrating how mediation can be an effective way of managing and preventing environmental conflicts (**Chapter 4.3**), let's look at the specificities of water-related environmental conflicts.

4.2 Water-related environmental conflicts

Water is widely recognized as a crucially important natural resource for the development of human societies. UN General Assembly resolution 64/292 (2010) "recognizes the right to safe and clean drinking water and sanitation as a **human right** that is essential for the full enjoyment of life and all human rights". The UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) also emphasise the importance of water resources. Most notably, SDG 6 seeks to ensure safe drinking water and sanitation for all, focusing on the sustainable management of water resources, wastewater, and ecosystems, and acknowledging the importance of an enabling environment. In the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, countries have committed to engage in systematic follow-up and review of progress towards the Goals and targets, using a set of global indicators.

However, to some extent, water has always been a contested resource and water conflicts and water wars have featured throughout human history. Water insecurity worldwide is increasing as populations grow, economies expand, and climate change impacts intensify. In many places, the growing water insecurity is combined with other societal stressors. As a result, the incidence of water-related conflict appears to be growing (**Figure 2-3**).

Figure 2. The Trend in Incidences of Violence Associated with Water Resources and Water Systems, 1930 to 2018

Source: Gleick (2018)

Water can play different roles within a conflict:

- a) Water can be a **trigger** of conflict, particularly in relation to **control** or **access** to water resources. The term “**water grabbing**” refers to “situations where powerful actors take control of valuable water resources for their own benefit, depriving local communities whose livelihoods often depend on these resources and ecosystems” (Franco et al., 2014).
- b) Water can become a **weapon** of war, e.g. when one party exerts control over water resources to the detriment of the other party.
- c) Water can become a **casualty**, e.g. when key water infrastructures become a military target.

Generally, the strategies to reduce water-related conflicts can be summarized in four broad categories (Iceland, 2020):

1. **Natural resources, science, and engineering approaches.**
2. **Political and legal tools**, such as minimum river flow requirements to halt over-extraction; transboundary and subnational water-sharing agreements; international humanitarian laws; land and water-rights reforms...).
3. **Economic and financial tools**, such as water pricing.
4. **Policy and governance strategies**, such as processes of collectivization/“**communing**” (Ostrom, 1990); **water diplomacy**... Keskinen et al. (2021) identify 5 key aspects of water diplomacy (**Figure 3**): political, preventive, integrative, cooperative, technical.

Figure 3. Five key aspects of water diplomacy

Source: Keskinen et al. (2021)

The suggested **Water Diplomacy Paths approach** envisions possible ways forward through four main steps:

1. Identification of **key themes** and related **actors**. The main water diplomacy actors typically consist of riparian country governments and related intergovernmental organisations such as river basin commissions, often coupled with other actors across multiple diplomacy tracks. Water diplomacy actors may also include so-called third-party actors such as external countries, networks or organisations involved in the water diplomacy process.
2. Analysis of the **current state**.
3. Recognition of (undesired) **drivers** and related **scenarios**.
4. Identification of possible **water diplomacy actions**.

4.3 Mediation within environmental conflicts: how and why

Collaborative practices such as **mediation** can be effective ways of managing and preventing environmental conflicts. This type of conciliation path differs from those usually used in the civil and commercial fields in many respects. In particular, the application of environmental mediation can have the following impacts:

- **Reducing time** compared to judicial and administrative procedures
- **Reducing costs** (avoiding the trial in court, reducing legal expenses, reducing waiting times and avoiding the interruption of activities which affect or are affected by water issues)
- Improving the **effectiveness** and **duration** of the agreements. Indeed, agreements that involve the participation of stakeholders are more likely to be respected, unlike the decisions imposed by a court that do not consider local specificities and interests.
- Ensuring **flexibility** and **adaptability**, as the agreements among different parties can always be reviewed and adapted to new environmental conditions, new needs and changed social conditions
- Promoting **social cohesion** and **learning** experiences by implementing new forms of sharing and discussions among actors in relation to the management of common goods such as water resources. During a mediation process, environmental conflicts are **deconstructed and rebuilt** through tools and processes of **deliberative participation** (Figure 4).

Figure 4. An iterative process of participatory deliberation

Mediation processes generate inclusive, shared, legitimate decisions that are endorsed by both authorities and social communities if the following conditions are met:

- The process is supported by **external and unbiased experts**, who work **with** the parties, rather than for the parties.
- The process ensures **information-sharing**, inclusive **communication** and **dialogue**.
- **Stakeholders** are carefully selected, ensuring wide and representative participation.
- The final decision is not imposed (top-down) but collaboratively elaborated by the engaged stakeholders (**bottom-up**).
- The process is **iterative** and characterized by **reflexive monitoring**.

A mediation process is generally characterized by three main phases: pre-negotiation, negotiation, and post-settlement.

4.4 Alternative Dispute Resolution Systems in Italy, Greece, Turkey and Tunisia

4.4.1 Mediation in Italy

According to Italian law (art.1, D.lgs. n. 28/2010), **mediation** is "the activity carried out by an impartial third party and aimed at assisting two or more parties in the search for an amicable agreement for the settlement of a dispute, even with the formulation of a proposal for its resolution". Mediation has as its main objective the search for a **conciliatory agreement** that allows the settlement, shared and with lasting effects, of a dispute thanks to the achievement of a solution that all the parties consider fair and satisfactory. Environmental mediation also allows promoting a method of **coexistence** that allows the continuation of the relationship between the parties and that contributes to the creation of a community between subjects who share the same territory.

A **mediator** is defined as "the person or individuals who, individually or collectively, carry out mediation without, in any case, the power to make judgments or decisions binding for the recipients of the service itself". The mediator's goal is therefore to facilitate dialogue, to circulate information, to make the parties feel welcomed and listened to, to share the rules and the progress of the procedure with the parties and thus create the conditions so that a climate of trust begins to emerge that allows the negotiation to unfold. If deemed necessary, in the face of technically complex issues, a mediator can be supported by external experts.

Below is a summary of the main stages characterizing a mediation process:

1. Application

A **subject** (natural or legal person, public body, association, committee, etc.), using the appropriate forms, submits an **application** to the Mediation Body containing their data, the subject of the conflict, the questions, the parties involved, potentially interested parties, any ongoing judgments (criminal, civil, administrative), and any additional information deemed useful.

The **Mediation Body** contacts all the interlocutors, verifying their willingness to participate in the mediation process.

The Mediation Body then appoints the mediator and sets the date of the first meeting.

2. Pre-mediation

By "pre-mediation" we mean the set of contacts or meetings, including informal ones, that the mediator has with the parties to analyse the conflict, define the objectives, identify the relevant stakeholders and plan the mediation process.

3. The mediation process

Mediation cannot be conceived as a rigid procedure. It should rather be a tool in the hands of the parties. The entire mediation process should not last more than 3 months but the term can be extended by mutual agreement between the parties.

The mediation (i) must be an expert in conflict management and in the facilitation of multi-stakeholder tables; (ii) does not necessarily have to possess specific knowledge on the subject matter of the dispute, although this is appropriate or required; (iii) is designated on the recommendation of the Mediation Body and must be and be considered by the parties to be neutral and independent.

4. Post-settlement

When the mediation is successful, the parties undertake commitments regarding future actions, to be carried out, and which are indicated in the signed document. At this point, the mediation is formally concluded. However, the correct execution of the decisions taken constitutes proof of its effectiveness. It is therefore appropriate that in the mediation agreement shared methods of control and **monitoring** of the commitments undertaken are provided, as well as the resolution of disputes that may arise in the executive phase.

4.4.2 Mediation in Greece

Law 3898/2010 introduced the concept of mediation as an alternative way of resolving disputes, domestically and internationally, between either individuals or states.

Law 4512/2018 made an effort to transform voluntary mediation to "mandatory", i.e. before an in-court discussion, the parties were obliged to try to resolve their dispute through mediation, or the case would have been inadmissible. However, mandatory mediation contradicted to the spirit of voluntarism that should inform alternative dispute resolution systems. Law 4512/2018 was deemed unconstitutional (as it breached Article 20 Paragraph 1 of the Greek Constitution, which asserts that "everyone has the right to be provided with legal protection by the courts...") and never entered into force.

According to the current legislation (Law 4640/2019):

- Mediators must be accredited by the Ministry of Justice.
- No legal background is necessary.
- There are two kinds of mediation:

- i. **Voluntary mediation**, i.e. any civil or commercial matters, labour cases, customer relations, domestic violence.
- ii. **Mandatory ‘First Attempt Session’ Mediation**, i.e. one initial session with a mediator/family cases, civil claims involving more than €30,000, and contractual disputes (mediation clause).

There also may be special forms of mediation:

- i. **Financial Mediation** – The New Bankruptcy Code (Law 4378/2020) – provides for instances of out-of-court debt settlement mediation.
- ii. **Family Mediation** – Reform of Family Law to incorporate Law 4640 (Law 4800/2021) - mediation in cases of parental responsibility disputes.
- iii. **Cadastral Mediation** - Law 4821/2021 entitled ‘Modernization of the Hellenic Cadastre’ introduces instances of mediation

Lastly, there may be **informal mediation mechanisms**:

- i. The Committees for the Amicable Settlement of Consumer Disputes.
- ii. The Hellenic Financial Ombudsman: Non-profit Alternative Dispute Resolution Organisation (HFO ADRO, formerly HOBIS), member of the European Financial Dispute Resolution Network (FIN-NET) for cross-border disputes.
- iii. The Mediation and Arbitration Organisation (O.M.E.D.) for collective labour disputes.
- iv. The Labour Inspectorate (S.E.P.E.) for the settlement of individual labour disputes.

4.4.3 Mediation in Turkey

Turkish Mediation Law on Civil Disputes (“Act 632517”) was adopted on 22 June 2012 and came into force on 22 June 2013. Article 137 of Civil Procedure Law provides that judges, at a preliminary hearing, are required to ask the parties about having voluntary mediation before a court proceeding.

There may be several forms of mediation:

- i. **Employment Mediation**: the new Labour Courts Code (2018) provides mandatory mediation as a pre-condition to a lawsuit where the parties should apply for mediation in order to solve their labour disputes before filing a lawsuit.
- ii. **Commercial Mediation**: the law on legal procedures to initiate proceedings for monetary receivables arising out of subscription agreements (“act no. 7155”) (2019). Moreover, as of 01 April 2022, Turkey ratified the Singapore Convention on Mediation (United Nations Convention on International Settlement Agreements Resulting from Mediation), which applies to international settlement agreements resulting from mediation, concluded by parties to resolve a commercial dispute.
- iii. **Consumer Disputes Mediation**: in 2020 amendments were made to the Consumer Protection Law.

Mandatory mediation was first introduced in 2018. In the event of specific employment, monetary/commercial and consumer disputes, parties must apply for mediation before bringing the case to court. Parties have the right to choose their mediator from a registered list.

The average length of a mediation session depends on whether the mediation is voluntary or mandatory. Time limits are set for mandatory mediation (3 weeks in case of

employment disputes and 4 weeks in case of commercial disputes), while no time limits are set for voluntary mediation. However, usually, parties have three months to resolve their dispute out of court through mediation. If the parties cannot reach an agreement, they can request a further three months. The parties must complete the mediation proceeding by the end of this total period.

Executing a settlement agreement is not sufficient to make it enforceable. To enforce a settlement agreement, the parties should obtain an **annotation on the enforceability** of the agreement from the competent court. An annotation on the enforceability of the agreement is like a decision given by a court.

4.4.4 Mediation in Tunisia

Tunisia does not have a general legal framework governing recourse to mediation for resolving disputes. However:

- The president of a commercial chamber may charge one of the chamber's members to help parties settle the dispute amicably (Art. 40 of the CCPC).
- District Courts' judges are bound to incite parties to explore an amicable agreement before the commencement of any adversarial proceedings (Art. 45 of the CCPC).
- Mandatory sessions of judicial settlement constitute a threshold procedure in any divorce proceedings (Art. 32 of the Family Law Code).

In practice, the efficiency of judicial settlement as an amicable dispute resolution mechanism has been curbed relatively, due to (i) courts' congestion on the one hand and (ii) judges' inadequate training to handle this kind of non-adversarial dispute resolution mechanism.

More recently, there have been attempts at raising awareness about mediation's benefits, as well as instances of internationally sponsored programmes supporting mediation and peacebuilding at the local, regional and national level.

5 Case studies

The approach of the Acqúa Summer School combined theoretical and practical activities. Four role-play simulations of mediation processes were organized, with case studies about **water-related conflicts from the Mediterranean Region**: Arborea, Sardinia; Malia, Greece; Erdemli, Turkey; Wadi El Bey, Tunisia.

5.1 Arborea, Sardinia

Arborea is the main **dairy cattle district** and a **nitrate-vulnerable zone** in Sardinia.

The simulation for the Arborea case study was inspired by a traditional Sardinian practice of peaceful dispute resolution, the *Rasgioni* (The Reason). Traditionally, *La Rasgioni* was used as a public mediation process for reconciling two parties whenever a conflict, often regarding property or livestock, could not be solved in other ways.

LA RASGIONI

IL TRIBUNALE DEL CAMBIAMENTO

Arborea, Hotel Le Torri, lun 27 giugno 2022, ore 16:30

Five people were involved in the process of reconciliation: two *Alligadori* (lawyers) who represented the interests of each party; two *rasgiunanti* (judges), and the *omu di mezu* (arbiter). Once the *Alligadori* had presented their speeches, the *rasgiunanti* examined relevant documents and afterwards were called to pronounce their final verdict. Two solutions were possible: *dizisa* if the request of one of the parties was accepted; or *arrangiu* when a compromise solution was suggested. Everyone could attend the debate, thus turning private conflicts into collective public events and creating learning opportunities for the whole community.

The *Rasgioni* scheme, already used by the Desertification Research Center of the University of Sassari in the processes of stakeholder engagement, proved to be useful in bringing out the problems in the agro-environmental field and in facilitating the opening of learning spaces.

On the first day of the Acqúa Summer School, an event was hosted involving local stakeholders. The event was titled "*La Rasgioni: il tribunale del cambiamento*" (**The Reason: the court of change**). 19 stakeholders were involved as key witnesses and asked to publicly tell their stories and the reasons informing their practice, in front of a team of scientists willing to understand the nature of the issues and provide critical reflections. Representatives of the Institutions (e.g. Regional Agriculture Department, Municipality of Arborea, Regional Agencies of the Hydrographic District, Environmental Protection Agency, Sardinian Water Authority, Land Reclamation Consortium of Oristano, University of Sassari and Cagliari), local production realities (Dairy Cooperative, Farmers Cooperative, Livegreen, Fishermen Cooperative), environmentalists and citizens were invited to "reason" about:

1. **Current state:** strengths and weaknesses of the Arborea socio-ecological system; key decisions and measures that led up to the current situation.
2. **Future scenarios:** pathways for the future; key investments to be made and measures to be taken.

The event proved successful by creating an **innovative dialogical space** that enabled stakeholders and researchers to collectively identify opportunities and barriers for mitigating nitrate pollution of groundwater resources and promoting sustainable development and climate change adaptation.

5.2 Malia

The catchment of Malia is in northern Crete, Greece, 40 km east of the city of Heraklion. Surface water and groundwater are used to support the extensive agricultural activity in the area, while in the last 20 years the increased touristic development has raised significant water consumption demands. The water resources in the area are very important for its residents as they cover their drinking water needs, as well as their welfare, depending on the agricultural and touristic activities that consume large amounts of water. Thus, groundwater levels have been significantly depleted over the last 30 years causing extensive groundwater saltwater intrusion. The water quality in the area has been significantly depleted due to extensive saltwater intrusion of the aquifer. Therefore, high Cl⁻ concentrations are found in groundwater which in conjunction with over-pumping result in low aquifer levels and groundwater degradation. In addition, increased nitrates concentrations are also found in groundwater due to the extensive agricultural activity in the area.

The main stakeholders include:

- Waste Management Company of Voreia Pediada
- Decentralized Administration of Crete
- Directorate of Water
- Region of CRETE
- Organization for the Development of Crete S.A.
- Hersonissos Municipality
- Social Ecological Cultural Network Associations of Hersonissos Municipality (KOIPODI)

5.3 Erdemli, Turkey

The Erdemli coastal aquifer (ECA) is located about 30 km west of Mersin (South-Eastern Turkey), covering an area of 45 km². The main problems in the region are the intensive use of groundwater, decrease in quantity and quality of surface and groundwater due to increasing droughts, agricultural activities and untreated wastewater discharges.

The main stakeholders include:

- Erdemli Kocahasanlı Irrigation Association
- Mersin Environment and Urban Planning Directorate
- Erdemli Municipality
- Erdemli Reeves Association
- Erdemli District Directorate of Agriculture and Forestry
- Local agricultural producers

5.4 Wadi El Bey

The Wadi El Bey pilot site is located at about 40 Km at the south of Tunisian capital. It extends over a surface of 430km². The site is characterised by a high level of pollution as a result of the important development of the industry, agriculture and tourism activities. The main sources of pollution are industrial and agricultural activities and inadequate wastewater treatment. Despite this legal framework, various industries discharge their inappropriately treated wastewaters in this Wadi, which represents a serious threat on the shallow groundwater quality.

The main stakeholders include:

- Public authority: BPEH (Office of planning and hydraulic balance of Ministry of agriculture, hydraulic resources and fishery);
- ANPE (National agency of environmental protection);
- Regional agricultural authority (CRDA Nabeul);
- Territorial agricultural authority (CTV Grombalia);
- Local authority: Municipalities of Soliman and MenzelBouzelfa;
- Water utility: ONAS (The national sanitation utility); SONEDE (National water distribution utility)
- Water users associations
- Industries
- The Agency of Extension and Agricultural Training (AVFA)
- APAL (Coastal Protection and Planning Agency)

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6 Additional learning material

6.1 Suggested readings

Franco J., Kishimoto, S., Kay, S., Feodoroff, T., Pracucci, G. (2014). The Global Water Grab: a primer. https://www.tni.org/files/download/the_global_water_grab.pdf

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Temper, L., Demaria, F., Scheidel, A. et al (2018). The Global Environmental Justice Atlas (EJAtlas): ecological distribution conflicts as forces for sustainability. Sustainability Science, 13, 573–584. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-018-0563-4>

6.2 Additional learning material

The **Environmental Justice Atlas** (EJA) documents and catalogues social conflict around environmental issues: <https://www.ejatlas.org/>

IHE Delft Institute for Water Education is the largest international graduate water education facility in the world: <https://www.un-ihe.org/>

The “Basin at Risk” project provides a quantitative, global-scale exploration of the relationship between freshwater resources and conflict, as well as indicators to measure cross-border tension: <https://transboundarywaters.science.oregonstate.edu/content/basins-risk>.

IHE Delft Interview with Professor Aaron Wolf, water diplomacy and peace expert: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H5SyqIRlv3I>

IHE Delft Alumni Online Seminar: Water Cooperation & Diplomacy: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9mtuNqW0f5o>